

**Report
on
Seed Diversity, Germination, Plant Standing and Harvesting**

**PART-2
RABI SEASON**

**State Name: Jharkhand
Third Reintroduction of Farmer's Varieties
2022-2023**

Fig.: Mixed Cropping Barley, Mustard and Pea; Passbook Number 01-003

**Submitted To
FAO, ITPGRFA IV CYCLE PROJECT**

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Under the project

Improving pulse biodiversity in rice fallow areas of tribal belts of Central and East Indian states to bring resilience in the farming practice, provide livelihood support and enhance nutritional level of the tribal population.

Seed Biodiversity Report

Time Period for Sowing: NOVEMBER 2022

Crop name	Variety name	Seed in CSB (For sowing)	New seed improved	New seed Local/ Haat	Total seed	Passbook no. (seed distribution)	Passbook no. For Reporting Under trial
Black mustered	Barun kvk	5kg	0	10kg		006,007,008,004,0023,035,056,065,015	002
Black mustered	Pusa bold	2.5kg	0	4kg		0010,0012,	0010
Yellow mustered	Rajendra.kvk	3kg	0	3kg		002,009,013	002
Yellow mustered	Chandan haat	1kg		5kg		002,004.009,007,013	002
Chana	GNG1998	2.5kg				004,003	003
Chana	Chandan.haat	3kg		5kg		004,0024.026.028.30,	004
Masoor	Jasidih haat	2kg		5kg		003,005,007,09	003
Masoor	Arun	1kg				012	012
Masoor	DI 406 kvk	1kg				0017	0017
Masoor	Jasidih haat	2kg		10kg		021,023,36,046,0024,045,0	0021
Mater	P10	2kg		3kg		003,004,005	003
Barly	Jayoti	2kg		5kg		003,006,009,31	003
		25 kg		50 kg			

Total Seed in Circulation **75 kg**

Germination report:

Crop: Chana, Masoor, Pea, Barley

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 003)

Passbook No.	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing date	Date of Germination 50%	Any pest attack	Water logging	Other vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestions
003.1	chana	Gng/kvk	24/11/2022	6/12/2022	No	No	No	yes
003.2	masoor	Jasidih haat	“	6/12/2022	“	“	“	
003.3	Matar/Pea	P 10	“	8/12/2022	“	“	“	
003.4	Berle	Jyoti	“	4/12/2022				

Crop: Mustard
Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 002)

Passbook No	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing date	Date of Germination 50%	Any pest attack	Water logging	Other vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestions
002	black mustard	barun kvk	22/11/2022	4/12/2022	no	no	no	yes
002	Yellow mustard	rajendra	“	“	“	“	“	
002	Yellow mustard	chandan haat	“	“	“	“	“	

Crop: Mustard, Chana, Masoor
Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 010, 004, 012, 017, 021)

Passbook No.	Crop Name	Variety	Sowing date	Date of Germination 50%	Any pest attack	Water logging	Other vulnerable factor	Scientist suggestions
0010	Black mustard	Pusa,bold	23/11/2022	4/12/2022	NO	No	No	yes
004	chana	Chandan,haat	23/11/2022	3/12/2022	“	“	“	“
0012	Masoor	Arun	25/11/2022	6/12/2022	“	“	“	“
0017	masoor	DL 406	25/11/2022	5/12/2022	“	“	“	“
0021	masoor	Jasidih ,haat	27/11/2022	6/12/2022	“	“	“	“

A/c No 012; image: Masoor	A/c No 017; Image: Masoor
A/c No. 010; Image: Black Mustard	A/c no 004; Image: Chana

Plant Standing report:

Crop: Black Mustard, Chana, Masoor

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 0010, 004, 0012,0017,0021)

Trial plot no. /pass Book no	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
0010	Black mustard	78%	45%	No	No	yes	No
0004	Chana	75%	25%	'	'	"	"
0012	Masoor	65%	35%	'	'	"	"
0017	Masoor	50%	40%	'	'	"	"
0021	masoor	45%	30%				

A/c no 004; Image: Chana

A/c no 0010; Image: Black Mustard

A/c no. 0012; Image: Masoor

A/c no 0017; Image: Masoor

A/c no 0021; Image: Masoor

Crop: Black Mustard, Chana, Masoor
Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 0003)

Trial plot no. /pass book no 814142-01-0003	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
003.1	Chana	75%	20%	No	No	yes	No
003.2	Masoor	70%	15%	‘	‘	‘	‘
003.3	Mater	55%	10%	‘	‘	‘	‘
003.4	barely	80%	5%	‘	‘	‘	‘

Trial no 003.4; Image: Barley

Crop: Black Mustard, Chana, Masoor
Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 0003)

Trial plot no. /pass book no 814142-01-0002	Crop name and variety	No. of plants stand	% of plants with flower	Any disease observed in plants so far	Water logging	Contact with scientist	Other vulnerable factor
002 Trial 1	Black mustard	56%	20%	No	No	yes	No
002 Trial 2	Yellow mustard	70%	35%	‘	‘	‘	‘
002 Trial 3	Yellow mustard	65%	20%	‘	‘	‘	‘

<p>Yellow Mustard</p>	<p>Yellow Mustard</p>
<p>Black Mustard</p>	<p>Black Mustard</p>

Pod and Harvesting report:

Crop: Black Mustard, Chana, Masoor
 Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 0010, 004, 0012,0017,0021)

Trail plot no/passbook no.-814142-01-003	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plants	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
003-1	Chana Gng /kvk	20/2/2023	2-3	35-55	NO	26/3/2023	2kg	White	No
003-2	Masoor Jasidih haat	21/2/2023	1-2	25-40	Yes	27/3/2023	3kg	White	“
003-3	Mater (Pea) P10	18/2/2023	4-7	20-40	NO	20/3/2023	2kg	White	“
003-4	Barley Jyoti	17/2/2023	30-45	6-10	no	30/3/2023	2kg	white	“

Trial no 1; Image: Chana	Trial no 2; Image: Masoor
Trial no 3; Image: Mater (Pea)	Trial no 4; Image: Barley

Crop: Mustard

Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 002)

Trail plot no/passbook no.-814142-01-002	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plant	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
Trial no 1	Black Mustard, Baun kvk	14/2/2023	5-8	40-60	No	22/3/2023	3kg	White	No
Trial no 2	Yellow Mustard, Rajendra, KVK	12/2/2023	6-10	35-60	No	15/3/2023	4kg	“	“
Trial no3	Yellow Mustard, chandan haat	11/2/2023	6-8	30-70	No	11/3/2023	3kg	“	“

Trial No 2 Yellow Mustard	Black Mustard
Yellow Mustard	

Crop: Mustard, Chana, Masoor
Trials on farmer's field (A/c no. 0010, 004, 012, 017, 021)

Trail plot no/passbook no.	Crop name variety name	Pod appearing date	Number of seeds per pod	No. of pod in a plants	Any disease observed plants so far	Harvesting of pods date	Quantity (kg) of seed got from trial plot	Color of pod and no of seed in pod	Other vulnerable factor
0010	Black mustard, Pusa bold	8/2/2023	6-10	50-70	No	24/3/2023	7kg	white	No
004	Chana, Chandan haat	18/2/2023	1-2	25-40	No	25/2/2023	6kg	White	''
0012	Masoor, Arun	18/2/2023	2-3	30-50	Yes	25/2/2023	8kg	White	''
0017	Masoor DI 406	16/2/2023	2-3	25-45	Yes	21/3/2023	5kg	White	''
0021	Masoor Jasidih haat	12/2/2023	2-3	30-60	yes	26/3/2023	10kg	white	''

A/c no 10; Image: Black Mustard	A/c no 04; Image: Chana
A/c no17; Image: Masoor	A/c no 12; Image: Masoor

A/c no 21; Image: Masoor